

NDAC/LO/047

1984 Dec 12

Tenth NDAC Report from Lund Observatory

WP6000-7000 Step 2/3 (S Söderhjelm, L Lindegren)

A draft description of the programs to simulate input data for Step 2/3 has been written and forwarded to FAST for their information. The tape format is still TBD, but general routines for transferring disk files to tape and back (e.g. in blocks of 2048 INTEGER*4) are being tested.

The general strategy for the formation and solution of normals has been described (C). Work continues on the development of these programs.

Working papers:

- C Söderhjelm 1984-10-20: SIP23: Programs to simulate input data for Step 2/3 (draft version)
- C Lindegren 1984-11-05: Step 2/3 Formation and Solution of Normal Equations (WP6240, 6260, 6270) (NDAC/LO/046)